

**FINE ACTIVITIES ARE THE MAIN TOOL OF AESTHETIC
EDUCATION OF CHILDREN AND THE RELATIONSHIP WITH OTHER
ACTIVITIES**

Rakhmatova Ikboldkhon Inomjonovna

Teacher of the Pedagogical Institute of Termez State University

Tursoanova Gulzoda Mamatali qizi

student of the Pedagogical Institute of Termez State University

Annotation: the factors influencing the development of thinking operations (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization) in children in the process of visual activity, as well as the systematic study of the connection of visual activity with other activities such as play, art reading and storytelling, music and so on. covered ways to go.

Keywords: visual ability, preschool, children's visual activity, subject of science, basic concepts, development, educational work with children, painting, clay, cutting and pasting, lessons, aesthetics, thinking (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization), cognition, creative development.

INTRODUCTION

The great Greek philosopher Socrates at that time called professional educators "obstetricians of thought." It is important to ensure that new ideas are born in the minds of children, not to announce the finished truth.

Visual activity is very important in the comprehensive education of school-age children. In order to draw or create an object, it is necessary to get acquainted with it or observe it in advance, to know its shape, size, location, color. In this process, sight, feeling, and hand movements are involved. In the process of observing and reviewing objects and events, children divide the object into large and small groups, change its shape, and describe its color in a variety of ways. Also, in the process of

visual activity, children get acquainted with different materials (paper, chalk, paints), their unique properties, techniques of working with them, which leads to the intellectual development of children.

It is known that in the process of visual activity allows children to develop thinking operations (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization), which in turn leads to the rational growth of children. In this process, children's speech develops. Applications are types of visual activities, the main function of which is the figurative reflection of the environment. The importance of visual activity in the implementation of sensory education is great. Because children are inextricably linked with objects, find them by their unique qualities, shape, color, size, identify their differences and similarities, which allows children to develop sensory, visual, figurative thinking . Visual activities educate children morally. In the process of visual activity, children are taught the qualities of the will - to finish the work, to set goals and strive to achieve them, to overcome difficulties, to help their peers. In the process of creating collective work, children are taught . In the process of evaluating work, children are nurtured such moral qualities as having a realistic attitude towards their peers, being happy with their work and the work of their peers.

It should be noted that the visual arts are the main means of aesthetic education of children. Separating the size, color, shape, and spatial location of each object is part of this aesthetic sense. The development of aesthetic sense in children is associated with a deeper sense of color, rhythm, and proportion. If children feel the color, the shape, its diversity, or not, they will enjoy the diversity of the color mix. The development of aesthetic perception in children, they learn to make an aesthetic assessment of the object in relation to some of its qualities. It develops in them an understanding of works of art, feelings and attitudes towards them.

Indeed, visual activities play an important role in preparing children for school. Knowledge and skills in painting, clay, and building materials are the basis for successful school art and labor lessons. It prepares them for learning activities: teaches them to listen to the teacher, to follow his instructions. One of the main reasons for this educational activity is to find the main and important solutions to

the problem. Controlling one's work in the visual arts also plays a role in school performance. The child is also psychologically prepared in the process of visual activity. At school: curiosity, curiosity, goal-orientedness, regular practice, and so on. Thus, the skills acquired in the process of visual activity are the basis for children to quickly enter the life of the school.

Visual activities are part of the whole educational work with children in preschool education. That's why it's important to be involved in a variety of activities and activities. The nature of the child's visual activity makes it possible. In painting, clay, and gluing, children reflect their impressions of their surroundings, events, works of art, and songs. Education increases the effectiveness of educational work, children's interest in various activities

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is important to systematically link visual activities to other activities such as play, art reading and storytelling, music, and so on. First of all, it is necessary to ensure the interdependence of painting and clay cutting and gluing exercises. This has a huge impact on the aesthetic upbringing of children. The purpose and objectives of the clay and plasticine classes at MTT are to acquaint children with the basics of sculpture and to teach them practical skills. Brief information about sculpture. Sculpture is a form of fine art. A feature of this type of art is the size and shape of the image. Circular sculpture is not the only type of plastic painting. There are also bas-reliefs and high-reliefs, the relief circle is reflected on a flat surface, in contrast to the sculpture. These types of sculptures are used to decorate dishes, facades, interiors, etc. The classes use materials such as clay, plasticine, wax, and make various toys, animals, birds, and fairy-tale characters. Toys are one of the oldest forms of decorative art, and in ancient times, clay objects have survived. With the development of industry and culture in our country, the range of toys and their images is getting richer every year. There are many different materials used to make toys. But preference is given to mud. Clay is the main material in making things.

References

1. Nurmatova M.SH. Khasanova SH.T. Methods of drawing and teaching children to draw. "Cholpon" T: .2010y.
2. O. Hasanbaeva et al. Family pedagogy. T.: "Aloqachi", 2007.
3. "Is your child ready for school?" methodical manual. T.: , 2001.
4. Причины, повышающие творческие способности студентов на занятиях по созданию портрета. И Рахматова - Учёный XXI века, 2016
5. Место и значение игры в процессе художественного воспитания.
И Рахматова - Ученый XXI века, 2016
6. Practical Application of Prospects Rules in Drawing.II.Rakhmatova A'zamjon N.Valiyev.2018.Germany 82-85
7. COMPETENSE APPROACH IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM
TM, Rakhmatova I. Образование и наука в XXI веке (А3-20211130-420)